

Combining Grid, Cloud and Volunteer Computing

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Author:
Manos Katsomallos

Supervisor:
Ioannis Charalampidis

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Project Specification

Testing and further developing an infrastructure based on CernVM that enables launching jobs on volunteer nodes, cluster nodes and commercial cloud nodes. This technology will support a CERN educational game called Virtual Atom Smasher.

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Abstract

Due to hardware and parallelization constraints, distributing resource demanding computational tasks and assigning them to a grid of commercial or volunteer private nodes is a one-way solution. The cloud is undeniably the model that will, if it has not already, dominate in the field of computing. Numerous new cloud services appear constantly in the literature and the ones that were once state of the art are currently ported there. It is pretty much straight forward that the exploitation of such practices is critical for any notable effort. The purpose of this project was to combine the aforementioned entities, take advantage of top notch technologies and motivate citizens to participate in mass computing campaigns by offering the resources that they have in their possession.

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1 Introduction

Grid computing¹ is the collection of computer resources from multiple locations to reach a common goal. In the grid computing model, servers or personal computers run independent tasks and are loosely linked by the Internet or low-speed networks. Computers may connect directly or via scheduling systems. Grid computing is distinguished from conventional high performance computing systems such as cluster computing in that grid computers have each node set to perform a different task/application. Grid computers also tend to be more heterogeneous and geographically dispersed thus, not physically coupled. Most applications for grid computing projects have no time dependency, and large projects typically deploy across many countries and continents.

Cloud computing² is a model for enabling ubiquitous network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources. Cloud computing and storage solutions enables companies to consume computing resources as a utility (like electricity) rather than having to build and maintain computing infrastructures in-house. It relies on sharing of resources to achieve coherence and economies of scale, similar to a utility over a network. At the foundation of cloud computing is the broader concept of converged infrastructure and shared services.

Volunteer computing³ is a type of distributed computing, in which people donate their computing resources (such as processing power and storage) to one or more projects. Volunteers are typically members of the general public who own Internet-connected personal computers. Organizations such as schools and businesses may also volunteer the use of their computers. Projects are typically academic (university-based) and do scientific research, but there are also exceptions.

In this work, we test and integrate a component of the CernVM⁴, a baseline Virtual Software Appliance for the participants of CERN LHC experiments, the CernVM WebAPI⁵ used to control VMs, with the Virtual Atom Smasher^{6,7}, an interactive educational game that encourages people to delve into science.

¹ wikipedia.org/wiki/Grid_computing

² wikipedia.org/wiki/Cloud_computing

³ wikipedia.org/wiki/Volunteer_computing

⁴ cernvm.cern.ch

⁵ github.com/wavesoft/cernvm-webapi

⁶ github.com/wavesoft/virtual-atom-smasher

⁷ test4theory.cern.ch/vas

2 Virtual Atom Smasher

The Virtual Atom Smasher is a pilot project of the Citizen Cyberlab⁸ European research program. It is an interactive educational game that invites citizens to learn more about high energy particle physics, takes them inside the Theoretical Physics group (TH) of the Physics department (PH) at CERN, and gives them access to the same resources with the scientists.

The players can select specific parts of the quantum simulation machine, tune the available parameters and perform Monte Carlo simulations, just like the scientists at CERN do. During the process and while advancing in the game, relevant information about the events and stages come up. By interacting, learning and experimenting, citizens collaborate with each other and the scientists helping them do their research.

2.1 Components

This project consists of a large number of components. Managing dependencies between modules is a major concern throughout the development process. In order to organize its components to improve the speed and quality of the code RequireJS⁹ is used. It is a JavaScript automatic dependency resolution file and module loader optimized for in-browser use. Simply put, it provides the framework to write reusable, "autonomous" JavaScript modules and offers the means to describe dependencies between them. It can also be used in other JavaScript environments, like Rhino and Node.

Below in Figure 1, is demonstrated an example of the jQuery implementation using RequireJS inside any project.

```
requirejs.config({
  baseUrl: 'js/lib',
  paths: {
    // This example is using
    // jQuery 1.9.0 located at
    // js/lib/jquery-1.9.0.js,
    // relative to the HTML page.
    jquery: 'jquery-1.9.0'
  }
});

define(['jquery'], function($) {
  // Define the module
  var module = {
    foo: function() {
      // TODO: Do something
    }
  };
  // Return what this module exposes
  return module;
});
```

Figure 1. jQuery module definition and usage.

2.2 Styling

For optimally structuring the styling of the webpages of the application, LESS¹⁰, an open-source JavaScript extension to CSS, is utilized. It is a dynamic style sheet language that can be compiled into Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and run on the client-side or server-side. Influenced by Sass, it has influenced the newer "SCSS" syntax of Sass, which adapted its CSS-like block formatting syntax. The indented syntax of LESS is a nested metalanguage, as valid CSS is valid LESS code with the same semantics. LESS provides the following mechanisms: variables, nesting, mixins,

⁸ citizencyberlab.eu

⁹ requirejs.org

¹⁰ lesscss.org

operators and functions; the main difference between LESS and other CSS precompilers being that LESS allows real-time compilation via `less.js` by the browser.

For example in Figure 2, LESS gives the ability to use nesting instead of, or in combination with cascading. The resulting code is more concise, and mimics the structure of our HTML.

```
// CSS                                // LESS
#header {...}                          #header {
#header .navigation {...}              ...
#header .logo {...}                    .navigation {...}
                                        .logo {...}
                                        }
```

Figure 2. Style sheet comparison.

2.3 Templates

When developing modern HTML applications, we often write chunks of HTML code and dynamically insert them into the DOM using JavaScript. The tight coupling of UI and data logic does not promote separation of concerns and reuse. It makes the application harder to write and harder to maintain.

```
var html = "<h1>Hello</h1><p>World!</p>";
document.getElementById("container").innerHTML = html;
```

Figure 3. Using the HTML DOM `innerHTML` property.

In our project we use `Mustache.js`¹¹ as a template engine that can be easily used in any customization package. It is an open source logic-less (do not contain any if-else conditions or for loops) template system that provides templates and views as the basis for creating dynamic templates. Views contain the data to be included in the templates as JSON. Templates contain the presentation HTML or data with the template tags for including view data.

```
<script id="template" type="x-templ-mustache">
  <h1>Hello</h1>
  <p>{{name}}!</p>
</script>
```

Figure 4. The `template.mst` file.

```
function foo() {
  $.get('template.mst', function(tpl) {
    var data = Mustache.render(tpl, {name: "World"});
    $('#container').html(data);
  });
}
```

Figure 5. Use template with `jQuery`.

¹¹ mustache.github.io

2.4 Computing Resources

For the players' simulations to be performed, LiveQ¹² is used. It is a job distribution and monitoring framework with real-time feedback, control and full network awareness. The framework shown in Figure 6, is modular and designed to be fully scalable. In this way and by utilizing the CernVM WebAPI, simulation tasks can be executed on players' devices that wish to contribute their computational resources.

Figure 6. LiveQ architecture.

2.5 Outcome

The results of our work shown in Figure 7, indicate that the philosophy of the game remains the same, whereas, the user interface has been noticeably upgraded. A comprehensive and more concise user menu has been established. We integrated the new graphics created by the artwork designer and content developer of the game, Lioumpa Theodoridou. Last but not least, we introduced a new, comprehensible leveling system.

Figure 7. The main screen of the game before (left) and after (right).

¹² github.com/wavesoft/LiveQ

As far as the gameplay and user experience are concerned, in the simulation screen, there is a better metric visualization. The player can view live histogram updates and explanations of the tuning results. Finally, everywhere in the game, immediate handy assistance is offered with text pop-ups and informative help screens.

2.6 User Feedback

Shortly after the development of the game finished we invited volunteers to participate in a campaign where they would play the game for some time and afterwards express their opinion. Both their experience and knowledge acquired are taken into consideration. Currently, we are collecting this information and soon after, we are going to report and evaluate the results of the survey.

3 CernVM WebAPI

The CernVM WebAPI is an application that can interface with any browser in order to provide real-time interaction with a virtual machine running in the host operating system. This plugin identifies the hypervisors installed in the system and picks the most appropriate to host the VM. It then provides a simple interface to control the VM and access its configuration.

3.1 Architecture

Figure 8 displays the various components taking place in a typical CernVM WebAPI usage scenario:

Figure 8. CernVM WebAPI components.

- The **Application Website** is the website that wants to use the CernVM WebAPI. The application logic is written in JavaScript. For all the high-level operations it uses the `cernvm-webapi.js` library.
- The **Application Webserver** (in addition to serving the website) provides the Virtual Machine Configuration Point (VMCP), which is used to provide the configuration information for the virtual machine.
- The **CernVM WebAPI Daemon** is the binary application installed in the user's computer and is the one the JavaScript library interfaces with.
- The **CernVM Webserver** is the webserver inside CERN from which required information and data regarding CernVM WebAPI are stored.
- The **Hypervisor Website** is the website from which an appropriate hypervisor is downloaded from.
- The **Hypervisor** is an application installed in the user's computer and is the one where Virtual Machines will run.

Figure 9 shows the states of the VBoxSession Finite-State machine:

Figure 9. VBoxSession Finite-State machine.

3.2 Static Code Analysis

CernVM WebAPI is still a beta project under development, currently undergoing Coverity¹³ static code analysis¹⁴. Static code analysis commonly refers to the running of static code analysis tools that attempt to highlight possible vulnerabilities within 'static' (non-running) source code by using techniques such as taint analysis and data flow analysis.

Ideally, such tools would automatically find security flaws with a high degree of confidence that what is found is indeed a flaw. However, as highlighted in the previous section, where the system overview of the framework was briefly discussed, CernVM WebAPI consists of numerous components and its function is quite complex. Therefore, there are dynamic cases and logical errors that static code analysis cannot cover. That is why we decided to conduct unit testing¹⁵.

For optimal, platform independent unit testing results we used:

- Google Test¹⁶
- CMake¹⁷
- CTest¹⁸

3.3 Unit Testing

Unit testing is a software testing method by which individual units of source code, sets of one or more computer program modules together with associated control data, usage procedures, and

¹³ coverity.com

¹⁴ wikipedia.org/wiki/Static_program_analysis

¹⁵ wikipedia.org/wiki/Unit_testing

¹⁶ code.google.com/p/googletest

¹⁷ cmake.org

¹⁸ cmake.org/Wiki/CMake/Testing_With_CTest

operating procedures, are tested to determine whether they are fit for use. Intuitively, one can view a unit as the smallest testable part of an application. In procedural programming, a unit could be an entire module, but it is more commonly an individual function or procedure. In object-oriented programming, a unit is often an entire interface, such as a class, but could be an individual method. Unit tests are short code fragments created by programmers or occasionally by white box testers during the development process. It forms the basis for component testing.

The primary goal of unit testing is to take the smallest piece of testable software in the application, isolate it from the remainder of the code, and determine whether it behaves exactly as we expect. Each unit is tested separately before integrating them into modules to test the interfaces between modules. Unit testing has proven its value in that a large percentage of defects are identified during its use.

At a high-level, unit testing refers to the practice of testing certain functions and areas – or units – of our code. This gives us the ability to verify that our functions work as expected. That is to say that for any function and given a set of inputs, we can determine if the function is returning the proper values and will gracefully handle failures during the course of execution should invalid input be provided.

For example, if we have two units and decide it would be more cost effective to glue them together and initially test them as an integrated unit, an error could occur in a variety of places:

- Is the error due to a defect in unit 1?
- Is the error due to a defect in unit 2?
- Is the error due to defects in both units?
- Is the error due to a defect in the interface between the units?
- Is the error due to a defect in the test?

Finding the error (or errors) in the integrated module is much more complicated than first isolating the units, testing each, then integrating them and testing the whole.

3.3.1 Google Test

Google Test is a framework for writing C++ tests on a variety of platforms (Linux, Mac OS X, Windows, Cygwin, Windows CE, and Symbian). Based on the xUnit architecture. Supports automatic test discovery, a rich set of assertions, user-defined assertions, death tests, fatal and non-fatal failures, value and type-parameterized tests, various options for running the tests, and XML test report generation.

3.3.2 CMake

CMake is a cross-platform, free and open-source software for managing the build process of software using a compiler-independent method. It is used in conjunction with native build environments such as make, Apple's Xcode, and Microsoft Visual Studio to control the software compilation process using simple platform and compiler independent configuration files. It is designed to support directory hierarchies and applications that depend on multiple libraries. It has minimal dependencies, requiring only a C++ compiler on its own build system. CMake generates native makefiles and workspaces that can be used in the compiler environment. It is possible to support complex environments requiring system configuration, pre-processor generation, code generation, and template instantiation.

3.3.3 CTest

CTest is a testing tool distributed as a part of CMake. It can be used to automate updating (using CVS for example), configuring, building, testing, performing memory checking, performing coverage, and submitting results to a CDash or Dart dashboard system.

There are two basic modes of operation for Ctest:

- In the first mode, CMake is used to configure and build a project, using special commands in the CMakeLists.txt file to create tests. CTest can then be used to execute the tests, and optionally upload their results to a dashboard server. This is what is handled in this tutorial.
- In the second mode, CTest runs a script (using the same syntax as CMakeLists.txt) to control the whole process of checking out / updating source code, configuring and building the project, and running the tests. This is handled in CMake Scripting of CTest.

3.4 Current Status

After we integrated¹⁹ Google Test to the project using CMake, currently we are writing and performing unit tests for the libCernVM²⁰ component. It is a cross-platform library for starting, controlling and interfacing with Virtual Machines, mainly targeting desktop computers. It started as a browser plugin, using the NPAPI interface, but since it is getting deprecated, the logic was forked into an individual project, so it can be interfaced with newer implementations.

libCernVM takes care of three major interactions:

- Ensuring that a hypervisor is installed in the host's computer and is in functional state.
- Abstracting the interface with the hypervisor, ensuring integrity and security on the operations.
- Interfacing with the running VM instance.

¹⁹ kaizou.org/2014/11/gtest-cmake/

²⁰ github.com/wavesoft/libcernvm

4 Conclusion and Future Work

Combining grid, cloud and volunteer computing demands many different, yet interrelated tasks to be done. We visually upgraded the Virtual Atom Smasher and noticeably improved its gameplay. In parallel, the project's source code got polished and organized with a variety of techniques making it easier to read and maintain. Soon, players' simulations are going to run on their machines, using the CernVM WebAPI and utilizing local computational resources. For the CernVM WebAPI, we integrated it with Google Test using CMake and currently test the libCernVM component.

In the future, we are planning to evaluate player's feedback, finalize and make the new upgraded version of Virtual Atom Smasher publicly available. Additionally, we will further integrate Virtual Atom Smasher and CernVM WebAPI, and continue developing tests for more cases and components of the latter. Last but not least, we prepare to perform continuous integration using Jenkins²¹ an open source continuous integration tool written in Java.

²¹ jenkins-ci.org